

Photoperiod Impact on the Sexual Behaviours of West African Dwarf (WAD) Sheep in Dry Season

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Abstract: Photoperiod is the main environmental factor controlling the seasonality of reproduction in sheep by altering the production level of melatonin in the brain. The effect of photoperiod on sexual behaviours of our indigenous breed-most especially the West African Dwarf Sheep is yet to be fully ascertained owing to the fact that tropical temperatures remain relatively constant throughout the year. Twenty WAD sheep (10 ewes and 10 rams) aged 1-1.5 years, were allotted to two treatments: 12-hour and 9-hour. photoperiod exposure with each treatment having 5 rams and 5 ewes, for 15 days. Libido and oestrus of the rams and ewes, respectively were assessed using standard procedures. Libido response was higher in rams on 9-hour (60%) than those on 12-hour (20%) photoperiod exposure. Oestrus response was higher in ewes on 9-hour photoperiod exposure (80%) than those on 12-hour (0%) exposure. The results of the mounting enthusiasm in T1(12 hours of light) showed that 80% of rams did not mount, 20% gave a normal mount and 0% mounted with enthusiasm. In T2 (9 hours of light), 40% of rams did not mount, 40% gave an ordinary mount and 20% mounted with enthusiasm. The study of Photoperiod exposure showed that the lesser daily sunlight exposure can be beneficial in breeding of West African Dwarf (WAD) sheep in the hot dry season (non- breeding season).

Keywords: Photoperiod, West African Dwarf sheep, Libido, Oestrus.

Introduction

The reproductive characteristics of sheep can be influenced by the photoperiod (length of daylight), wherein a period of high sexual activity can be observed as the hours of daylight are reduced, while libido in rams and ewes decreases as the photoperiod is increased (Silva *et al.*, 2005). In temperate

regions, changes in photoperiod are one of the most important factors in seasonality, since they direct the secretion of gonadotropins, leading to periods of reproductive activity and inactivity. However, in low-latitude regions, commonly found in tropical and subtropical environments, the effect of photoperiod on reproduction is thought to be minimal

(Chemineau *et al.*, 1998). The Ewes have a distinct breeding season, their oestrus cycle generally starts when day length is decreasing and ends when day length is increasing. Although semen production continues throughout the year in rams, sperm quality is lower in the non-breeding season (Chemineau *et al.*, 1992). Breeding programmes in sheep are limited to the breeding season. The seasonality of breeding in West African sheep has affected year-round breeding and thus affecting economic value of sheep products and by-products. Information on controlling the breeding seasonality of West African dwarf (WAD) sheep with photoperiod regulation has not been adequately documented. Therefore, the effect of photoperiod on the sexual behaviour of WAD sheep was ascertained

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out at sheep unit of The Federal University of Technology Research Farm, Owerri Imo state on latitude 5°29'N and longitude 7°02'E in November. The region is in the South Eastern agro-ecological zone of the rain forest zone of Nigeria with a mean annual rainfall of 2200mm (Eroarome, 2009). A total of 20 (West African Dwarf) sheep comprising 10 ewes and 10 Rams, aged 12 - 18 months, with

the rams having an average weight of 14kg and ewes having average weight of 15.5kg were used for the experiment.

Animal feeding and management

The rams and ewes were housed in separate units within the sheep pen, fenced and with open space. They were dewormed and vaccinated against PPR prior to the treatment. The animals were fed grasses consisting of Guinea grass (*Panicum maximum*) and Elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*), with grains offal as supplements. Feed and water were provided at intervals

Experimental design

This study was done in two phases, which were to ascertain long photoperiod effect (phase 1) and short photoperiodic effect (phase 2) 20 sheep (10 rams and 10 ewes) were divided into two treatments on sex basis. Each sex was grouped into two treatments, T1 and T2 (5 animals per treatment). All animals in T1 were used to determine long photoperiodic effects which took 12 hours of natural light (6am-6pm daily). All animals in T2 were used to determine short photoperiodic effects which took 9 hours of natural light (6am-3pm daily). Feed and water were stopped by 3pm daily across the treatments. In this experiment, artificial

darkness was created by using blinds made from black polyethene material. It was constructed in such a way that it can be rolled up and down when necessary.

Study duration

This study lasted for 14 days. this was to establish estrous which will normally happen with shorter day length between 14-17 days during which exposure to light was properly monitored.

Assessment of sexual behaviour

Parameters assessed include: Oestrus, libido, reaction time and mounting enthusiasm in rams.

Oestrus assessment

Oestrus is the period of time in which the Ewe is ready to be bred. Oestrus was not detected in all experimental ewes before the photoperiod regulation experiment. Signs of oestrus were monitored by checking for redness of vulva, standing to be mounted at the introduction of ram and finally checking for vaginal excretions across the treatments. These were assessed twice daily, within the 14 days of the photoperiod experiment, onset and duration of oestrus was monitored and recorded properly. Percentage oestrus was

calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{Number of ewes on heat} \times 100}{\text{Total number of ewes in the treatment}}$$

Libido assessment

Libido is a term used to describe sexual drive in the male animal. Reaction time which was used to evaluate libido was measured as the amount of time between first contact with the ewe and the first mount expressed in seconds. At the end of the 14 days photoperiod, rams within a treatment were introduced to their ewe counterparts on heat, to evaluate libido. Percentage libido in rams, were calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{No of rams which mounted per treatment} \times 100}{\text{Total number of rams in the treatment}}$$

Mounting enthusiasm

Mounting enthusiasm is a measurement of behavioral enthusiasm during mounting which was scored from +1 to -1 as reported by Hoflack et al. (2006). Mean reaction time, and mounting enthusiasm were evaluated for the rams and properly recorded.

Results and Discussion

The result on the effect of photoperiod on oestrus and libido is presented on Figure 1. It was observed that after 14 days of photoperiod regulation, four out of five ewes (80%) exposed to 9 hours of natural light significantly exhibited heat period while none

of the ewes (0%) exposed to 12 hours of natural light experienced heat period. The onset and duration of oestrus and reaction time is as shown in Table 1. Onset and duration of oestrus in ewes on 9 hours of photoperiod was recorded as 20 ± 2 days and 36 ± 6 hours, respectively. Sixty percent (60%) of rams (3 out of 5 rams) on 9 hours photoperiod exposure gave a mean reaction time of 53.33 seconds while one ram (20%) on 12 hours light exposure gave a mean reaction

time of 110 seconds. The results of the mounting enthusiasm is as shown on Table 2, in T1 (12 hours light) four out of five rams (80%) did not mount, one ram (20%) gave a normal mount and none (0%) mounted with enthusiasm. In T2 (9 hours of light), two rams (40%) did not mount, two rams (40%) gave an ordinary mount and one ram (20%) mounted with enthusiasm.

Figure 1 Percentage oestrus (heat period) and percentage libido

Table 1 Percentage oestrus (heat period)

Total number of Ewes in a group	(T1) Number (Percentage) that showed oestrus signs on 12-hours photoperiod	(T2) Number (Percentage) that showed oestrus signs on 9-hours photoperiod
5	0 (0%)	4 (80%)

Table 2 Percentage libido

Total number of Rams in a group	(T1) Number (Percentage) that mounted on 12-hours photoperiod	(T2) Number (Percentage) that mounted on 9-hours photoperiod
5	1 (20%)	3 (60%)

Table 3 Effect of photoperiod on oestrus and reaction time in WAD sheep (n=1)

Parameters	(T1) 12-hours photoperiod	(T2) 9-hours photoperiod
Mean reaction time (sec)	110	53.33
Onset of oestrus (days)	NIL	20±2
Duration of oestrus (hours)	NIL	36±6

Table 4 Effect of photoperiod on mounting enthusiasm

Parameters	T1(12-hours light)	T2 (9-hours light)
No mount (%)	80	40
Ordinary mount (%)	20	40
Mount with enthusiasm (%)	0	20

Photoperiod has been found to regulate reproductive cyclicity in sheep, affecting oestrus in ewes and quality of semen produced by rams. Percentage oestrus, Libido and mounting enthusiasm were significantly influenced by photoperiod at 9-hours light exposure compared to those on 12-hours exposure. This supports the findings of Maitre *et al.* (2006) who reported that the timing of

reproductive activity in sheep depends on the measurement of photoperiodic time and that the annual variation in photoperiod has strong predictive value of seasonal activities, especially reproduction in most animals. This finding further supports the works of Vivien (1985) who said that the environment plays an important role in the regulation of reproduction in different animals, quoting that among various components of the

environment, annual changes in the duration of the solar day (photoperiod) has been proved to be the primary variable that individually, or in combination with other environmental factors determine the sexual periodicity in most animals. This suggests that at reduced light intensity, absorption of light by the melatonin receptors in the retina was inhibited; causing a reduced excitation of the superior cervical ganglion (SCG) which relayed to the pineal gland to produce endogenous melatonin, this increase in melatonin production gives rise to increased production of GnRH producing LH and FSH. In vertebrates, melatonin is a conservative chemical signal of light-dark cycles of the environment (Cassone *et al.*,1993). In all animal species investigated so far, melatonin production is high during the night time and low during the day time (Collen *et al.*,1989). In a similar study by Senger (2003) and

Chemineau *et al.*, (1992) with exotic breeds, successful breeding was reported during the shorter photoperiods.

Conclusion

In temperate regions, changes in photoperiod (length of daylight) are one of the most important factors in seasonality, however in tropical and subtropical environments, the effect of photoperiod on reproduction is thought to be minimal and requires more study to understand why our indigenous WAD cannot still produce all year round.

The study of Photoperiod exposure showed that 9 hours daily exposure of light can be beneficial in breeding of West African Dwarf (WAD) sheep in the hot dry season (non-breeding season), since it induced oestrus up to 80% and libido up to 60% in ewes and rams, respectively.

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